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Deliverable D3.2 Continuous DAS and SOP waveforms and parametric data archive, delivered through EIDA nodes and HCMR for solid earth and marine communities

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Abstract

SUBMERSE has successfully recorded fibre optic sensing data using three different technologies, DAS, SOP and SOP OTDR, on 5 sites across Europe. Most of these sites continue recording. Data is being stored on facilities provided by SUBMERSE partners. Two calibration experiments using OBS were also conducted.

This deliverable reports on the data collection sites and experiments, providing for each one the following information: i) data type and main characteristics; ii) recording periods; iii) data storage; iv) data availability, v) current and future data recording status.

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1 Executive Summary

One of the main objectives of SUBMERSE WP3 (Proof of concept exploitation) was to distribute reduced DAS, SOP and SOP-OTDR data sets generated by WP2 allowing for the development of higher level data products to be used by a wide range of research communities, using established data distribution structures (EPOS-EIDA, Copernicus-Marine). In parallel, WP3 have conducted validation experiments using standard instruments at sea and on land, whose data will also be made available. The main purpose is to foster the scientific and societal use of the DAS and SOP data generated by SUBMERSE. This goal is achieved by involving several key institutions, in particular EPOS ERIC (European Plate Observing System), represented through European Integrate Data Archive (EIDA) nodes GFZ, NOA, UiB and candidate node IPMA, and Copernicus Marine and EMSO ERIC (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory), represented through HCMR, FC.ID, CIENCIAS), thereby reaching a larger community across the geosciences and marine sciences. The planned strategy for opening the data for the scientific community begins by making the reduced and scrubbed data streams available. These streams will be provided in formats and on platforms that the respective communities are already familiar with, and which largely fulfil the criteria of FAIR data distribution (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

The main activities involved: i) preparing the infrastructure and procedures within EPOS-EIDA nodes for the distribution of continuous reduced data and metadata. Data will be provided in formats standard to seismology and the wider solid earth science (EPOS) community. Metadata will adhere to best practices established by the GeoInquire project; ii) preparing the derived oceanographic data for integration into the oceanographic European databases Copernicus Marine and EMODnet. This step includes assigning the necessary metadata to each dataset; iii) conducting calibration and validation experiments for a duration of few months using ocean bottom deployments around the Funchal-Sines and the Svalbard cables, utilising instruments from the German (DEPAS) and Norwegian pools, respectively; iv) validating the oceanographic data using established resources including moored oceanographic buoys and existing calibrated local models.

This Deliverable reports the status of the fulfilment of this main objective, namely detailing the type and volumes of data collected and their mode of access to the SUBMERSE research team and the global scientific community. Data collection, storage and distribution is a dynamic process, and while additional achievements are expected by the project's end the information contained herein is accurate as of the reporting cutoff date, October 31st, 2025.

SUBMERSE has successfully recorded fibre optic sensing data using three different technologies, DAS, SOP and SOP OTDR, on 5 sites across Europe. Most of these sites continue recording. Data is being stored on facilities provided by SUBMERSE partners and made available to SUBMERSE, after sensitive information was removed for security reasons (where applicable). Some data samples were also disseminated to external stakeholders, and the DAS recording sites are now connected to real-time data transmission links. Two calibration experiments with Ocean Bottom Seismometers were also conducted and the data recorded will be made available through EIDA nodes. DAS derived proxies for oceanographic data (significant wave height and surface currents) were investigated and their distribution via international data servers analysed. These data were not yet shown to be mature for a general distribution.

2 Introduction

SUBMERSE under WP2 planned to make data acquisition on several cables using 3 different technologies, DAS, SOP and SOP-OTDR while WP3 planned several calibration/validation experiments with new data collected by OBS and land stations. Additional calibration data was collected from public data servers like Copernicus or EIDA nodes.

The Table below summarizes the data collection sites and experiments, each of them to be described in detail in the following sections. For each data entry we provide the following information: i) data type and main characteristics; ii) recording periods; iii) data storage; iv) data availability, v) current and future data recording status.

Site Name	Cable A end	Cable B end	Cable type	Experiments / Calibration	Status	Partners
Svalbard, Norway	Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard	Longyearbyen, Svalbard	2 semi-parallel 256 km cable legs, repeaterless	DAS	ongoing	NTNU
				SOP	ongoing	NTNU
				OBS, GSN land station	OBS completed	UiB
Preveza, Greece	Preveza, Greece	Crotone, Italy	320 km cable, terrestrial repeaters	DAS	ongoing	NOA, GFZ
				SOP	Not recording	NOA
				SOP-OTDR	Not recording	NOA
				land stations	Ongoing	NOA
Rhodes, Greece	Rhodes, Greece	Samos, Greece	200 km cable, terrestrial repeaters	DAS	ongoing	NOA
				land stations, Tide gauge	Ongoing	NOA
Sines, Portugal	Sines, Portugal	Fortaleza, Brazil	5962 km cable, deep sea submarine repeaters	DAS	Ongoing	INESCTEC, GFZ
				SOP	Ongoing	EllaLink
				SOP-OTDR	Ongoing	EllaLink
				OBS, current meter, land stations, nearby moored buoys	30-10-2024 to 26-2-2025	FCUL, GFZ
Madeira, Portugal	Funchal, Madeira*	Sines, Portugal	1116 km (GeoLab 56 km) cable, deep sea submarine repeaters	DAS	ongoing	FCUL, GFZ, INESCTEC
				land stations, nearby moored buoys	ongoing	FCUL, GFZ
*NB: the Madeira cable has a separate dedicated fibre cable for DAS use built into the cable system which runs for 56 km, and does not reach the branching unit repeater						

3 DAS recorded at Madeira Site

An OptoDAS interrogator was deployed in October 2023 on a ~57 km fibre from the Praia Formosa Cable Station to the deep Madeira basin (Figure 1). The fibre used is provided by ELLALINK, under the scope of GeoLab. It is part of the Madeira branch of the main cable that extends from Fortaleza, Brazil, to Sines, Portugal. Emacom, the local partner, has provided field support and made rack space available.

Figure 1: Approximate location of the GeoLab fibre on the Madeira branch of the EllaLink cable.

The interrogator was configured with a 10 m gauge length, 5 m spatial sampling, and a 500 Hz sampling rate, for a total of 11293 channels. The acquired data are stored locally in 10-second HDF5 files. Since June 2024, data is synchronized with GPS and acquisition became continuous. Data collection was intermittent prior to June 2024 however, due to storage and bandwidth constraints data has not been fully archived. In July and August 2025, data was also collected at sampling rates of 1000 Hz for one week, and 1600 Hz for two weeks.

A SEEDlink stream to IPMA was established in May 2025. Data from 20 channels along the cable are streamed at 500 Hz via a dedicated SeisComP plugin (developed as part of the SUBMERSE project in cooperation between ASN and GFZ). These decimated channels are assigned the temporary seismic network code 3X (10.14470/8K802502) registered with FDSN. New software and firmware versions installed in June 2025 will allow to decimate the dataset directly at the interrogator and perform spatial averaging to improve the SNR. Configuration of the new software is still ongoing.

Raw data are stored locally on the OptoDAS system using a 77 TB RAID storage RAID and are periodically uploaded to an S3-compatible storage at INESC TEC with 1 PB capacity. A dedicated 1 Gbit fibre connection provided by FCCN and GEANT, links the interrogator server, IPMA, INESC TEC, and FCUL, where a remote-control terminal is installed. Currently, there are 191 TB of raw DAS data from the Madeira site uploaded to the S3 storage at INESC TEC, with the longest semi-continuous recording from December 2024 to June 2025. Interruptions for maintenance and updates ranged from a few hours to three days. Depending on storage availability, not all data will be preserved. Preserved datasets will generally be made publicly available two

years after acquisition, barring legally mandated scrubbing. These datasets are used for seismological, oceanographic, and biological research in the Madeira basin, complementing the observational capabilities of the Oceanic Observatory of Madeira.

An important result from the Madeira site is that one week of data, totalling 7 TB, collected between October 26th, 2023, and November 3rd, 2023, was uploaded to GEOFON for permanent storage. It comprised of full-temporal/spatial resolution HDF5 10-second files, with companion miniSEED files spatially decimated to 200 m and down-sampled to 250 Hz. This dataset has access restrictions until December 31st, 2025. The locations of the virtual receivers along the cable were extrapolated from publicly available sources.

This was the first submarine DAS dataset uploaded to GEOFON and helped establish data and metadata guidelines for future submissions, including the availability of decimated and down-sampled data in miniSEED format, embargo periods, and how confidential cable coordinates should be handled.

4 Sines recording site & calibration

4.1 DAS

A C-band OptoDAS system, provided by ASN, was deployed on May 27th, 2025, in a submarine fibre optic cable originating at EllaLink's cable landing station (CLS), connecting Sines, Portugal, to Fortaleza, Brazil. Figure 2 illustrates a representative section of the submarine cable route.

Figure 1: Representative location of the submarine cable that links Sines (Portugal) to Fortaleza (Brazil).

The cable is 5962 km long and contains deep-sea submarine repeaters along its entire length. The interrogator was configured with a 6.1 m gauge length, 1 m spatial sampling, and a 1.6 kHz sampling rate, providing a total

of 53,025 channels. Acquired data are stored locally in 10-second HDF5 files. The data acquisition server synchronizes its system clock over a VPN connection to a remote time server.

A dedicated 1 Gbit fibre link, provided by FCCN and GÉANT, connects the interrogator server to INESC TEC. Raw data are stored locally on the OptoDAS system using a 77 TB RAID storage array and are periodically uploaded to an S3-compatible storage system at INESC TEC, with a total capacity of 1 PB.

Currently, 136 TB of raw DAS data from the Sines site have been uploaded to the INESC TEC S3 storage. Interruptions for maintenance and updates have ranged from a few hours to a few days. Depending on storage availability, not all data will be preserved. Preserved datasets will generally be made publicly available two years after acquisition, except where legally mandated scrubbing applies.

4.2 SOP

As part of the established project partnership, and due to the unavailability of the Fast Telemetry software as well as the absence of a full network access—restricted for security reasons—the only feasible method for obtaining data from Infinera was through the manual sharing of datasets. These datasets were made available following Infinera’s internal safety evaluation process.

Consequently, Infinera kindly provided several sets of SOP and RF-SOP data, which were distributed by EllaLink to INESC TEC. The total volume of data amounts to approximately 51 GB, currently stored in INESC TEC’s MinIO object storage system. This dataset is available internally to SUBMERSE partners on request.

Fast Telemetry SOP Sample

This is a sample dataset recorded using the Fast Telemetry system in a laboratory environment at Infinera. The primary objective was to evaluate the structure and type of information available before broader sharing. The sample serves as a demonstration of SOP data collection capabilities.

RF Data

This dataset originates from a 90 MHz radio-frequency pulse transmitted along a submarine cable containing 81 repeaters. Each repeater reflects the RF phase, allowing for the calculation of phase differences between the original and reflected signals. These files include both in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) components. The data was recorded at the Sines CLS between August 20th and 31st, 2024.

Combined RF and SOP Data

This dataset includes both RF and SOP data, recorded at the Sines CLS during two periods: January 18th to 26th, 2025, and March 16th to 20th, 2025. The RF files contain in-phase and quadrature information. The SOP data is acquired using a similar method but captures the Stokes parameters (S₀, S₁, S₂, S₃) at each repeater. Additionally, the SOP of both the original and reflected RF pulses is recorded for analysis.

4.3 OBS Calibration experiment

IDL/FCiencias.ID/FCUL was the leader of the Ocean Bottom Seismometer (OBS) campaign off the coast of Sines as part of the European SUBMERSE project. On the morning of October 30th, 2024, the operations began with the deployment of seven OBS 100 km west of Aljezur in SW Iberia, close to the Ellalink submarine Cable (Figure 3). The expedition sailed from the naval base in Alfeite, near Lisbon, Portugal, aboard NRP D. Carlos I. The deployment coordinates were defined following a meeting with Ellalink representatives, who raised concerns

about the security issues surrounding a potential intervention on the cable. Consequently, OBS had to be deployed at least three times the water depth away from the cable. The coordinates were further refined to steer clear of the path of another submarine cable operated by ALTICE.

The 7 OBS were provided by the DEPAS pool managed by the Alfred Wegener Institute (Germany). Their dimensions are length x width x height: 1650 mm x 1070 mm x 720 mm and their weight in the water is 30 kg. The ballast is 700 mm x 500 mm, made of iron (which oxidises quickly in salt water) and weighs 70 kg out of the water. The deployment of the seven OBS started on October 1st. The sequence was SUB07, SUB05, SUB06, SUB04, SUB01, SUB02 and SUB03. The first one started at 00:01 UTC (01:01 local time) and ended at 04:19 UTC (05:19 local time). The datalogger programming was completed during the assembly of the OBSs, where we defined four channels (H, 2, 1, Z) with a sampling rate of 250 Hz on a 128 GB disk within the OBSs deployed in positions SUB07, SUB06, SUB05, SUB03, SUB02, and SUB01. Each OBS in these positions has a hydrophone (HTI-04-PCA/ULF) with a frequency response in the interval of 100 seconds to 8 kHz, a Trillium compact OBS seismometer with a corner period of 120 seconds, and a data logger (6D6) from KUM. The OBS with the current meter was deployed in position SUB04, using a different datalogger (the old MCS datalogger from SEND) with a different sampling rate (100 Hz) and 20 GB of disk capacity. However, this OBS has an identical hydrophone and seismometer. The current meter is a Seaguard RCM without additional sensors, and it was decided to sample the current every 10 minutes due to considerations of power consumption, disk space, and the campaign's duration.

On the morning of February 25, 2025, the campaign began to recover the seven OBS. The team departed from the naval base in Alfeite, near Lisbon, Portugal, on board the same vessel, the NRP D. Carlos I. On February 26th, at 08:34, we recovered the first OBS (SUB03). The recovery order was SUB02, SUB01, SUB04, SUB06, and SUB07, with the last one being SUB05 at 20:30.

All the OBS were recovered, and the data retrieval from the datalogger was successful. After decompressing the data, it was converted into miniSEED daily files with four different channels (@ 250 Hz): CDH (hydrophone), CHZ (seismometer vertical), CH1 (seismometer horizontal, linked to the North), and CH2 (seismometer horizontal, linked to the East) for each of the six OBS. The OBS installed in SUB04 features (@ 150 Hz) an HDH (hydrophone), HHZ (seismometer vertical), HH1 (horizontal seismometer channel linked to North), and HH2 (horizontal seismometer channel linked to East). This OBS supplies also oceanographic current speed and direction data. The recording period started on October 30, 2024, and ended on February 26, 2025, producing 50 GB of data for each OBS, totalling 350 GB. During the conversion process, a quality check revealed that the hydrophone data from SUB01 was of poor quality, and some problems were also found in the hydrophone data from SUB06 and SUB07.

This dataset will be freely available at the EIDA.pt seismic server, initially distributed without any clock or orientation correction. The dataset will be updated to incorporate necessary time corrections, ensuring the accuracy of our analysis. Additionally, the metadata will be revised and corrected once the rotation study is fully completed, providing a clearer context for the collected data. These data were assigned the code 4S by the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN). The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is 10.7914/a63e-rv21 (Corela et al., 2024).

Figure 2: SUBMERSE OBS location 100 km offshore Aljezur, close to the Ellalink cable.

5 Data recorded in Svalbard site

In Svalbard two near parallel 260 km long standard telecom G.652D single mode fiber-optic cables, with landing stations at Ny Ålesund and Longyearbyen, have been instrumented for SOP and DAS recordings. The first portion of the cable is trenched on land. The following sections of the subsea portion of the cable are buried into soft sediments at 0–2 m below the seafloor; other sections are lying on the seafloor (Figure 4). The objective of this arrangement was to monitor the environment on two independent systems, using two different technologies. To compare DAS and SOP data with single point measurements, 3 OBS were deployed close to the Ny Ålesund sections of the cable.

Figure 1: Map of the two cables connecting Ny Ålesund and Longyearbyen.

5.1 SOP

In Svalbard we have four SOP devices installed: two devices (Polbox) delivered by Cesnet and two others (PM1000) delivered by Novoptel (owned by NTNU). All four are operated by Sikt. To allow event localization by SOP we have installed three White Rabbit Switches (WRS) for time distribution, to synchronize the SOP devices over both ends of the cable (2024). The borrowed timing-source (hydrogen maser) is provided by the Norwegian Mapping Authority eVLBI-node in Ny-Ålesund. The SOP recorded continuously from October 2023 to September 2024.

For security reasons, data recorded on this submarine cable needs scrubbing before making it available to SUBMERSE partners and the public. Proof of concept software was written which allows the identification of signals necessary for security clearance. Therefore, only very limited SOP data are accessible to SUBMERSE. None of the data from these sites have been cleared for public release yet.

First trials from Svalbard have shown that one SOP unit can generate 6-12 GB of data per day.

SOP data, after filtering, are available through National e-Infrastructure for Research Data owned by Sigma2 and operated by the Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services facility in Lefdal. A total of 80 GB of SOP data, encompassing 15 days, are currently available to SUBMERSE partners.

5.2 DAS

The first DAS interrogator, a C-band DAS equipment from ASN (OptoDAS), was installed in Ny Ålesund on the 2nd of June 2022, and has been recording data continuously since then, apart from some technical breaks. This interrogator is being operated by NTNU since 2023. Later we followed the work by installing a L-band DAS to compare the co-existing possibilities of DAS with ordinary telecommunication wavelengths and at the same time compare the L-band DAS sensitivity with C-band DAS. After the test, L-band DAS have been removed but C-band DAS is still running.

Recording takes place from approximately 60 to 135 km. The gauge length has primarily been kept to 8 m, but some recent data has been recorded using 2, 4 and 16 m gauge length. Sampling frequency varies from 625 Hz to 200 Hz depending on the signals being targeted. During the first 1.5 years, recordings were made at 625 Hz to understand and capture most of the signals detected along the fibre. After we mapped out these signals, we were able to reduce the sampling rate most of the time to decrease the data load.

In 2024 (September 12th) Alcalá university installed a low-frequency interrogator in Ny Ålesund that has been recording continuously apart from the period December 3rd to 5th, 2024. It continued recording till March 2025. The measuring length is 50 km, and the sampling rate is 20 Hz for a gauge length of 10 m. The "DAS-Alcalá-Chirped-Pulse-phi-OTDR" equipment was installed in the same cable as OptoDAS for seabed temperature measurements.

For security reasons, data recorded on the ocean needs scrubbing before making it available to SUBMERSE partners and the public. Proof of concept software was written which allows the identification of signals necessary for security clearance. Filtered DAS data is shared with all partners through Sigma2 storage facility in Lefdal. 20 TB of DAS data is currently available to SUBMERSE partners.

DAS generates a very large volume of data that can be as big as up to 7 TB per day. This means that one unit requires around 650 TB of storage of raw data, if we want to be able to keep the raw data in a secure storage for three months.

Using the ASN SeedLink plugin, a single DAS-channel from offshore Svalbard will be made available in real-time, down sampled to 20 Hz, to be shared with SUBMERSE partners and global users through the EIDA node hosted by UiB@EIDA. For these data the network code ZP_(2025) has already been reserved by FDSN^[1] and the DOI has been defined^[2]. The FDSN network description follows:

This data set contains one channel from distributed acoustic sensing data collected in 2025 and shared as part of the SUBMERSE EU project. It contains raw time-differentiated time data as recorded by an OptoDAS interrogator through a dark fibre in a submarine telecommunication cable. The cable is trenched into soft sediment 0-2 m below the seafloor. The length of the fibre interrogated varies over the acquisition period. The data contains a continuous data stream from one channel with some breaks due to unforeseen events (like power outages). This data set has no exact positioning data of the fibre optic cable because they are proprietary to SIKT. However, there are rough positions available on <https://www.norgeskart.no/> using the 'Nautic Charts Overview' basemap.

In 2024 several days of recorded data from this interrogator were made available to the SUBMERSE team. The data recorded on February 2023 is available from the repository created during the Global DAS Month of February 2023 (Wuestefeld et al., 2023). The original data was spatially and temporally decimated to 24.51 m and 100 Hz. The cable length monitored was 50 km. The gauge length was 8.17 m. Total file size is 865.6 GB.

^[1] https://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/ZP_2025/

^[2] [10.7914/8vhy-xa82](https://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/ZP_2025/10.7914/8vhy-xa82)

5.3 OBS

To compare signals from more conventional single point seismic sensors to those recorded with fibre optics (DAS and SOP) an experiment was conducted with three ocean bottom seismometers deployed in the fjord Kongsfjorden outside Ny Ålesund, Svalbard, near the DAS cable (Figure 5). The instruments were placed in a triangular configuration, with a distance of ~ 1 km, one close to the inner cable and two close to the outer DAS cable. The OBS are 4 component (broadband 3C 120 second seismometer and hydrophone) K.U.M. Nammu model. The coordinates and operation period are shown in Table 1.

Location name	Latitude	Longitude	Water depth (m)	Deployment date	Recovery date
A	78.9869	11.6397	300	18/10/23	28/08/24
B	78.9883	11.5925	280	18/10/23	28/08/24
C	78.9797	11.6083	270	18/10/23	28/08/24

Table 1: Overview of OBS locations and deployment period.

Figure 2: Location map of the three OBS in Kongsfjorden given by diamonds. The approximate position of the fibre optical communication cable is given by dashed pink lines. The cable reaches land near a Geodetic Earth Observatory. Ny Ålesund is located about a km further into the fjord.

The complete dataset recorded by the OBS is prepared for archival and redistribution through the EIDA node operated by the University of Bergen. For these data a network code has been reserved by FDSN^[1] and the DOI^[2] has been defined. The distributed data will be time corrected. Sensor orientation will be performed in late November, and metadata will be updated accordingly.

[1] 5W

[2] 10.7914/12vn-4z72

6 DAS recorded at Preveza site

A DAS interrogator has been deployed to sense a dark fibre between Preveza (Greece) and Crotona (Italy) through the Ionian Sea (Figure 6). The interrogated sector of the fibre extends from Preveza (land station where an ASN OptoDAS interrogator is installed) to the seabed over a about 100 km. The fibre used is provided by ISLALINK, which operates the IONIAN submarine system, covering a total distance of approximately 300 km without intermediate repeaters.

The OptoDAS system was deployed on February 25th, 2025, by teams from GFZ and NOA, with field support provided by ISLALINK engineers. The interrogator was configured with a 20 m gauge length, 10 m spatial sampling, and a pulse repetition rate corresponding to a 500 Hz sampling frequency. This configuration yields 14,002 channels, covering a maximum sensing distance of 142.992 km along the submarine cable in the Ionian Sea. The acquired data are stored locally in 10-second HDF5 files.

The real-time streamed data channels include decimated data at 100 Hz and 1 km spatial sampling streamed in real-time to the NOA data centre via a dedicated SeisCompP plugin. These decimated channels belong to the temporary seismic network code ZQ ([10.7914/nmw3-3k60](https://www.fdsn.org/network_codes/show.php?code=ZQ)) registered at FDSN.

Raw data are stored locally on the OptoDAS system using a 77 TB RAID storage RAID and are simultaneously duplicated to a local NAS with 114 TB RAID capacity. On June 3rd, 2025, the GFZ NAS unit was exchanged by NOA personnel with an empty one to ensure uninterrupted data acquisition and archiving. The full-resolution dataset is planned to be archived on the GRNET cloud infrastructure; however, the establishment of a terrestrial link between the Preveza site and GRNET has not yet been completed by GÉANT. Decimated data are stored on EIDA@NOA as these channels are streamed in real-time through a mobile link provided by the NOA seismic network. As no Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) has not yet been signed with ISLALINK and the SUBMERSE consortium partners, the locations of the virtual receivers along the fibre remain strictly confidential, and access to the data remains restricted.

The dataset is used to test the extension of real-time monitoring capabilities for earthquakes (e.g. for the Hellenic and Kefalonia transform zone) and other natural hazards in the region, as well as to test oceanographic applications.

Figure 1: Indicative sampling points along the fiber route between Preveza and Crotona in the Ionian Sea.

7 DAS recorded at Rhodes site

A DAS interrogator has been deployed to sense a dark fibre between Rhodes and Kos islands (Greece), traversing the southeastern Aegean Sea (Figure 7). The interrogated section of the fibre extends from the town of Rhodes, where an ASN OptoDAS interrogator is installed at the landing station, across a terrestrial segment of approximately 40 km on the island, and continues subsea for about 100 km. The fibre, provided by COSMOTE and leased from GRNET, spans a total distance of approximately 100 km between the two islands, passing near the active Nisyros volcano.

The OptoDAS system was deployed on February 12th, 2025 by ACN and GRNET engineers. The interrogator was configured with an 8.2 m gauge length, 4.08 m spatial sampling, and a pulse repetition rate corresponding to a 500 Hz sampling frequency. This configuration was covering a maximum sensing distance of 199.154 km along the submarine cable in the southwestern Aegean Sea. The acquired data are stored locally in 10-second HDF5 files. Unfortunately, the signal quality deteriorated significantly after the first 40 km, following the end of the terrestrial segment. The replacement of a potentially faulty fibre segment at the Kameiros Skala landing point may improve the signal quality. Alternatively, relocating the interrogator to the Kos island side is being

considered as a potential solution. As an intermediate measure, the interrogator was reconfigured on 8 July 2025 to acquire 20,002 channels, covering a maximum sensing distance of approximately 81.7 km—primarily along the terrestrial section of the cable on Rhodes Island. The real-time streamed data channels include decimated data at 100 Hz and 1 km spatial sampling streamed experimentally in real-time to the NOA data centre via a dedicated SeisComP plugin. These decimated channels do not belong yet to a temporary seismic network code registered at FDSN.

Raw data are stored locally on the OptoDAS system using an 80 TB RAID storage RAID. The full-resolution dataset is planned to be archived on the GRNET cloud infrastructure; however, this has not yet been completed. Decimated data are stored on EIDA@NOA as these channels are streamed in real-time through a terrestrial link provided by GRNET. A Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) has been signed between COSMOTE and NOA. As a result, the locations of the virtual receivers along the fibre remain strictly confidential, and access to the data continues to be restricted.

The dataset will be used to investigate subduction zone earthquakes along the southeastern Hellenic Arc and monitor seismic activity in the Nisyros volcanic field.

Figure 1: Indicative sampling points along the fibre route between Rhodes and Kos in the Aegean Sea.

8 Oceanographic data to marine communities

(a) Data dissemination flow for oceanographic DAS-derived signals

Over the last five years optical fibre sensing techniques, mainly DAS, have been in use to demonstrate monitoring capabilities of oceanographic signals. Thus far the oceanographic signals that are identifiable in DAS records are wind-induced ocean surface gravity waves, internal gravity waves driven by density gradients, ocean currents and marine mammal vocalizations (Table 2). In most cases listed in Table 2, the different oceanographic signals are diagnosed on DAS strain records based on their frequency ranges. Although strain signals at targeted frequencies are adequate for monitoring marine mammals, users interested in ocean surface waves and bottom currents require wave and current data of comparable characteristics and quality to that provided by existing observing platforms (Tables 3 and 4), and accessible through the primary European marine data services: Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS), European Marine Observations and Data Network (EMODnet), and European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO).

Figure 1: Data dissemination flow for the SUBMERSE project.

Figure 8 illustrates the suggested marine data dissemination flow for the SUBMERSE project, where the first step is to convert down-sampled strain data to one of the measured characteristics included in Tables 3 and 4. Two options are suggested for the conversion: on site, in Near Real Time (NRT) or (2) in delayed time (DT). The operational potential of converting DAS strain to oceanographic parameters on site, in near-real time (NRT) is in line with one of the project's key objectives, to deliver a "...continuous acquisition and dissemination system for European research infrastructures...". However, there are 3 limiting factors that complicate the delivery of NRT data:

1. security issues that might restrict public data use,
2. down sampling the vast volume of raw data to a manageable size,
3. ongoing development of methods for translating strain measurements into useable data such as wave or current information.

The limiting factors (1) and (2) have been discussed extensively in other WPs and although **the operational flow of DAS data remains a SUBMERSE objective**, it might be difficult to achieve within the lifetime of the project.

Table 2 lists the publications that compare oceanographic signals from DAS data to in situ observations, to show the status of progress towards extracting this type of data and converting DAS strain to oceanographic parameters (limiting factor (3)). For the case of ocean wave signals (OSGW and IW) combined, ~30% (4) of the studies include, mainly qualitative, comparisons to in-situ measurements. Furthermore, in just two of the wave related publications (Glover et al., 2024 and Meulé et al., 2024) a "1-1" quantitative comparison of DAS-derived versus in situ wave characteristic exists (namely significant wave height in both). For ocean bottom currents, all studies on Table 1 include DAS-derived ocean bottom current speeds and half of them include comparison to in-situ current measurements. Factoring in the novelty of trying to use DAS as an oceanographic

platform, there has been significant progress especially over the last three years and there are already suggested methods in literature for deriving wave and current characteristics from strain.

Ocean signals observed Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS)	Frequency	Publications	Comparison to in-situ observations
Ocean surface gravity waves (OSGW)	~0.05–0.5 Hz	Lindsey et al., 2019 Sladen et al., 2019 Landrø et al., 2022 Williams et al., 2022 Taweasantanon et al., 2023 Glover et al., 2024 Lin et al., 2024 Meulé et al., 2024 Song et al., 2024 Yang et al., 2025 Shi et al., 2025 Loureiro et al., (in press)	Yes Yes Yes Yes
Internal waves (IW)	~0.001–0.1 Hz	Pelaez Quiñones et al., 2023 Williams et al., 2023	Yes
Ocean bottom currents	<0.01 Hz	Williams et al., 2022 Mata Flores et al., 2023 Lin et al., 2024 Song et al., 2024 Spingys et al., 2024 a, b Ko et al., 2025	Yes Yes Yes
Marine mammal vocalizations	10 Hz–20 kHz (depending on the species)	Landrø et al., 2022 Bouffaut et al., 2022 Rørstadbotnen et al., 2023 Wilcock et al., 2023 Saw et al., 2025 Loureiro et al., (in press)	

Table 1: Summary of oceanographic use cases explored in DAS recordings.

Platform/Instrument	Measures	Measured Wave Characteristics
In-situ		
Wave Buoys	Surface motion via accelerometers/GPS	Hs Tp/Tm Wave direction Spectral energy density
AWAC (Acoustic Wave And Current profiler)	Doppler water velocity & surface tracking	Hs Tp/Tm Wave direction Directional wave spectrum
Pressure Sensors	Pressure fluctuations on seafloor	Hs

		Tp/Tm
Offshore Platform Sensors	Radar, lidar, pressure, laser	Hs Tp Directional wave spectrum
Remote sensing		
Satellite Altimeters (e.g., Sentinel-6, Jason-3)	Radar return time from sea surface	Hs Tm
SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar)	Sea surface roughness imaging	Wave direction- Wavelength 2D wave spectra
Scatterometers	Surface wind roughness via radar	Indirect wave state estimation

Table 2: Ocean surface wave observing platforms (in situ and remote sensing). Hs is the significant wave height, Tp/Tm are the peak/mean wave frequencies respectively.

Platform/Instrument	Measures	Measured Current Characteristics
ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler)	Doppler shift from particles in the water column	Current speed Current direction (multiple depths/vertical profile)
Current Meter (mechanical, EM, acoustic)	Flow at a fixed point using a rotor, electromagnetic induction, or acoustic Doppler	Current speed Current direction (single depth)
Moorings with ADCPs or Current Meters	Fixed moored lines with instruments at various depths	Current speed Current direction (discrete depths)

Table 3: Most used deep ocean current observing platforms (in situ).

(b) Requirements for data providers

Before DAS derived wave and current data, evaluated/calibrated against in-situ observations, can finally reach CMEMS, EMODnet or EMSO, it must fulfil the data provider requirements. Key common requirements for all data aggregators are the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and open access. Delivering FAIR data is in line with SUBMERSE objectives. The security restrictions on the raw DAS data, should not be of concern for the derived, down-sampled oceanographic data. Therefore, the SUBMERSE oceanographic data could be made publicly available. Other common requirements include the provision of metadata (i.e. ISO 19115 and INSPIRE standards), with geolocation being one of the most essential attributes. Providing precise geolocation information on DAS records is impossible, either in NRT or DT due to the security restrictions, however using coordinates that have been extracted from digitisation of cable maps, as the one on Figure 2 (Section 4.1), should suffice. Finally, data format requirements for data providers follow similar rules with the commonly accepted format being Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), while other supported formats can be “Comma Separated Value” (.csv) and Ocean Data View (ODV) formats.

In principle, data found in the CMEMS repositories are also found in the EMODnet repository since there is a signed MoU between these two partners. SUBMERSE marine data could be potentially hosted in either one. Since CMEMS is a leading force in operational oceanography and SUBMERSE aims to progress towards developing an operational flow of marine data, CMEMS can be the target data repository for DAS-derived

relevant datasets. EMSO works differently in hosting marine data than CMEMS and EMODnet, as it distributes data that are directly linked to its observatories (Figure 9).

To ingest SUBMERSE data, EMSO must contact the regional observatories closest to the SUBMERSE sites (namely Cretan Sea, Hellenic Arc, Iberian Margin, Nordic Seas) to discuss available options, if any. Hence, CMEMS can serve as the primary repository for SUBMERSE oceanographic data.

Figure 2: Geographic distribution of EMSO regional observatories (<https://emso.eu/observatories/#overview>)

(c) Status of disseminating DAS-derived marine data from the SUBMERSE project

(i) Advances in Deriving Oceanographic Parameters from DAS Records - Scientific Part

There are two reasons why the Madeira site is the focus of the oceanographic use cases tasks thus far: (i) data availability (Section 3), and (ii) the existence of moored buoy wave observations close to the cable's location, which enable comparisons between buoy-observed and DAS-observed wave characteristics.

Qualitative comparisons between the wave buoy's SWH and DAS signals demonstrate potential in establishing proxies for ocean wave characteristics (Loureiro et al., in press; Schlaphorst et al., in preparation). Ongoing work aims to derive the same wave characteristics from DAS records that are measured by buoys and satellites. An alternative methodology for deriving oceanographic variables directly from DAS measurements is evaluated by comparing the DAS-derived wave characteristics with the outputs from regional wave models (CMEMS Iberia-Biscay-Ireland Regional Wave Model).

The use of Theoretical Dispersion Curves for DAS signals within frequency ranges <0.5 Hz (Sladen et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2019; Song et al., 2024; Loureiro et al., in press; Schlaphorst et al., in preparation), may provide an alternative proxy for ocean bottom current magnitudes, but without simultaneous measured current estimates it is hard to evaluate them. Model outputs cannot be considered a direct substitute for in-situ measurements when comparing currents. This is because numerical models use the ocean floor as a boundary, imposing forced boundary conditions rather than estimating the true current values. To address the challenges posed by the lack of in-situ measurements, HCMR is planning to deploy an Acoustic

Wave And Current profiler (AWAC) near the Preveza site (coastal, 30m depths) by the end of 2025, as part of the SUBMERSE project using its own resources. Should such a deployment happen, it is expected to provide valuable datasets needed for applying tested methods (Glover et al., 2024; Song et al., 2024; Meule et al., 2024).

(ii) Advances in Deriving Oceanographic Parameters from DAS Records - Technical Part

An essential part for delivering SUBMERSE data to the marine repositories is to establish procedures that ensure manageable dataset sizes. Using the Madeira data, statistical methods have been applied to drop channels which are too noisy and reduce temporal resolution. Specifically, HCMR is currently reducing data to 100 Hz sufficient for oceanographic applications and coastal monitoring, and it is evaluating whether the reduction of sampling frequency to, e.g., 10 Hz, is a scientifically sound choice. Using a similar submarine fibre optic cable, a systematic process from downloading to providing meaningful oceanographic parameters is being built and will be adjusted to data from Preveza when it becomes available.

(iii) Marine mammals

Several baleen whale vocalizations are present in the GeoLab DAS and have been manually verified, as reported by Loureiro et al. (in press) and Pereira et al. (2025). For data screening and detailed signal detection, we generated lists of days with candidate signals using band-limited energy detection with a matched-filter cross-correlation, with the passband and master template tuned to each species' expected signal characteristics (Pereira et al., 2025). The selected days are being used to build reference annotations that will train more complex machine-learning models for automated multi-species detection. Although a dedicated European repository for marine mammal vocalizations does not exist yet, the inclusion of ocean sound among the Global Ocean Observing System's (GOOS) list of cross-disciplinary Essential Ocean Variables highlights the systematic and coordinated efforts of the ocean observing community and indicates the potential development of such a repository in the future. Data linked to this SUBMERSE use case could be made available upon request after they are published.

(iv) Future steps: contacting potential marine services to host SUBMERSE oceanographic data

An important next step is to contact CMEMS In-Situ Thematic Assembly Centre and start discussions on how DAS can be added as a new observing platform and/or strain as a new parameter. HCMR, due to its active involvement with CMEMS In-situ TAC can act as a contact between SUBMERSE and CMEMS. Some example points that can be discussed with CMEMS are:

1. What are the CMEMS in-situ products that could host the SUBMERSE DAS-derived wave characteristics, current magnitudes etc.?
2. What will be the quality control steps to be followed for the DAS-derived data and how can they be in-line with the standard CMEMS quality control steps that are performed for each in-situ product?

This discussion could start before the end of 2025, ensuring that progress is made before the end of the project.

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